

ENTREPRENEURS PERCEPTION ON SME SCHEMES OFFERED BY THE BANKING AND NON BANKING INSTITUTIONS IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

SME sector is the key area for marking the economic growth in our country. The rise in the SME sector plays an important role, especially in a developing country like our country India. The primary data needed for the study has been collected through well structured questionnaire. The sample size of 105 respondents was selected from Coimbatore District. The selected samples were tabulated and analysed analyzed using simple percentage, Chi square test, standard deviation and ANOVA. The study concluded that Indian Government and Tamil Nadu Government have taken various efforts to improve the economy by providing relief measures to the SME units to increase their number vis-à-vis improving employment opportunity, exports and Country's GDP.

Key Words: Entrepreneur, Perception, Banking, Schemes, Smes, Sector, Industrial, Etc.

Introduction:

A person who sets up a business or businesses, taking on financial risks in the hope of profit. An entrepreneur is an individual who creates a new business, bearing most of the risks and enjoying most of the rewards. The entrepreneur is commonly seen as an innovator, a source of new ideas, goods, services, and business/or procedures. Entrepreneurs are not risk-averse. They are willing to risk their time, money and even their reputation to get the business started and take their products or services to market. Entrepreneurs are also willing to take risks even after they establish a business, developing new products and approaches that can grow their businesses. Entrepreneurs are often people who are eager to question why and how things are being done even if these processes are clearly "industry-standard." This doesn't mean an entrepreneur should ignore industry best practices, but the entrepreneur is also willing to challenge these practices if she believes that there is a better way to do them. Persistence: Entrepreneurs are persistent. They aren't easily discouraged and are willing to work through discouragement and challenges. Entrepreneurs are willing to attend trade shows, meet with bankers, call on clients and do what it takes to get the business started, and then to make it successful. Entrepreneurs mobilize the idle savings of the public through the issues of industrial securities. Investment of public savings in industry results in productive utilization of national resources. Rate of capital formation increases which is essential for rapid economic growth. For this purpose Tamilnadu government have taken steps several steps for SMEs.

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) represent a vital part of the economic system, due to their significant positive impact on such macroeconomic indicators of the country as gross domestic product, employment, added value and revenue of the Tamilnadu state budget. SME sector is the key area for marking the economic growth in our country. The rise in the SME sector plays a important role, especially in a developing country like our country India. It is a main employment booster for many people, where they receive great financial benefits. Tamil Nadu is one of the most crucial states excelling in the SME sector. With its vivid and dynamic culture, it has given rise to small scale enterprises. However, the Tamilnadu government has also provided various incentives and rewards for the different industries, which has further enhanced the growth in the sector. The following sections give a detailed overview of the support of the Tamil Nadu government toward the SME sector.

Tamil Nadu is promisingly the land of opportunities, especially in the SME sector. It is full of people with excellent skills and the ability to deliver consistently and quality services. According to recent development, it is the third-largest Indian state in terms of the number of SMEs, with over five million micro, small, and medium-scale businesses. Tamilnadu has a total population of more than 72.14 million. The It's total exports currently stand at third position in the country's total exports, with around USD 46.46 Billion. Businesses have an excellent opportunity for establishing their businesses in the state. Apart from this, the customer base opportunities towards domestic goods. It also masters various crucial sectors like fruits, dairy, vegetables, spices, and poultry. When it comes to eye-catching opportunities, Tamil Nadu is an important hub of smart phones and electronics manufacturing. It also has an excellent infrastructure with decent road connectivity and amenities. Furthermore, the state has also garnered attention for being a central location for auto-components production with the presence of reputed engineering companies. Therefore, these are early signs of growth and market potential for SME businesses.

Review of Literature:

Sonfield, Matthew; Robert Lussier; Joel Corman; and Mary McKinney (2001) conducted a gender comparison testing of the Entrepreneurial Strategy Matrix, a situational model that suggests strategies for new and ongoing ventures in response to the identification of different levels of venture innovation and risk. They conclude that there are no significant gender differences in venture innovation/risk situations or in strategies chosen by business owners. Lindsay, Noel J.; and Justin Craig (Winter 2002) conducted a study focused on understanding how entrepreneurs recognize business opportunities and whether there is a difference in the opportunity recognition process between experienced entrepreneurs and private equity financiers of entrepreneurial ventures. They indicate that opportunities are seen in similar manner by those who have developed experience in the entrepreneurial context whether they are entrepreneurs or private equity financiers.

Michael, Steven C. (2003) argued franchising as a technique used by entrepreneurs in service industries to assemble resources in order to rapidly create large chains and gain first-mover advantage. Whether and how such first-mover is created is the subject matter of his study. He specified a structural equations model and empirical results from the restaurant industry support the model’s predictions that the first –mover advantage initially takes the form of a lead in the number of retail outlet, followed by a market share lead and, finally, superior profitability.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the demographic profile of entrepreneurs in Coimbatore District.
- To identify factors which influence entrepreneurs perception on SME schemes offered by the banking and non banking companies in Coimbatore District

Methodology Used:

Experimental / Descriptive Research:

Experimental/ Descriptive research includes surveys and fact findings enquiries of different kinds. The main purpose of descriptive research is a description of the state of affairs as it exists at present. The important feature of this type of research is that the researcher has no control over the variables. This research can only report what has happened or what is happening.

Type of Sampling:

Convenient sampling has been used for the purpose of drawing samples from the Coimbatore District.

Samples Size:

The sample size chosen by for the purpose of this study is 105 Entrepreneurs who offered SME schemes through the banking and non banking companies in Coimbatore District

Source of Data:

Data are collected for the studies are both from primary data and from secondary data

Primary Data:

Primary data are collected through surveys, interview, questionnaires and schedules. The primary data refers to the data collected from direct questioning and which has not been collected or gathered earlier by any other research study. The data for this study was collected from SME entrepreneurs.

Secondary Data:

This type of data refers to the gathering of information from the sources that have “readymade data” already in possession. This data has already been collected and compiled. data were collected from various sources including books, brochures, periodicals, websites publications, web site’s etc. which are noted in the reference. After gathering the data from the Sources, the data was analyzed, tabulated, interpreted and finally conclusions were made regarding the entire project.

Tools for Analysis and Interpretation:

The following are the major tools that were used by the researcher for analysis and interpretation.

- Percentage analysis
- Tabular and graphical analysis
- Chi-square analysis
- Anova test.

Limitations of the Study:

- The statistical method used to analyze the data has their own limitation.
- Due to time constraints and busy schedules of the people it was difficult to interact with them completely.
- All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1

Particulars	No. of Respondents n=105	Percentage
Gender		
Male	65	61.9

Female	40	38.1
Age		
18- 25	16	15
26- 35	36	34
36 -45	38	36
46 -55	15	14
Educational Qualification		
12 th or below	46	43.8
Graduate	39	37.1
Post graduate	20	19.0
Amount of Investment		
Upto Rs.10,00,000	16	15
Rs.10,00,001 to Rs.25,00,000	49	47
Above Rs.25,00,000	40	38
Total	105	100

Table 2: Relation between Age and Entrepreneur Perception

Age	Perception				Total
	Affordability	Better Service	Low Rate of Interest	Easy Repayment Facilities	
18- 25	2 (12.5%)	2 (12.5%)	2 (12.5%)	10 (62.5%)	16(100.0%)
26- 35	10 (27.8%)	10 (27.8%)	10 (27.8%)	6 (16.7%)	36 (100.0%)
36 -45	24(11.2%)	4 (11.2%)	22 (61.1%)	10 (27.8%)	38 (100.0%)
46 -55	0 (0.0%)	4 (26%)	9 (60%)	2 (14%)	15 (100.0%)
Total	14 (13.3%)	16 (15.2%)	43 (41.0%)	32 (30.5%)	105 (100.0%)

Hypothesis:

H₀: There is no significant difference between age and entrepreneur perception on SME schemes offered by the banking and non banking companies. After setting this null hypothesis for conducting chi- square test.

	Value	DF	Sig.
Likely Hood Ratio	40.003	12	.000
Pearson Chi Square	37.836	12	.000

Interpretation:

It is perceived from the table that the P value (0.000) lesser than the 0.05.so it is interpreted that there is significant difference between age and entrepreneur perception on SME schemes offered by the banking and non banking companies.

Table 3: Relation between Gender and Entrepreneur Perception

Gender	Type of Companies		Total
	Banking Companies	Non Banking Companies	
Male	33 (50.7%)	32(50.2%)	65 (100.0%)
Female	14 (35.0%)	26 (65.0%)	40 (100.0%)
Total	47 (44.8%)	58 (55.2%)	105 (100.0%)

Hypothesis:

H₀: There is no significant difference between gender and different form of investment. After setting this null hypothesis for conducting chi- square test.

	Value	DF	Sig.
Likelihood Ratio	26.515	3	0.000
Persons Chi-Square	22.379	3	0.000

Interpretation:

The table shows that the P value (0.000) lesser than the 0.05.so it is interpreted that there is significant difference between gender and different form of investment.

Conclusion:

Day by day, new enterprises and new entrepreneurs are introduced. It is a good sign for our country. Entrepreneurship development is not an easy thing. More research should be conducted for successful entrepreneurs. For this purpose SME sector has induced the economic activity in India and all over the world apart from providing self-reliance, sustainable economic development, eradicating poverty by providing employment opportunity to youths. Indian and Tamil Nadu Government have taken various efforts to improve the economy by providing relief measures to the SME units to increase their number vis-à-vis improving employment opportunity, exports and Country's GDP.

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